

REMOTE HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM FOR THE ESTIMATION OF BLOOD PRESSURE, HEART RATE AND BLOOD OXYGEN SATURATION LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design and implementation of an Internet of Things-based remote health monitoring system for the estimation of Blood Pressure (BP), Heart Rate (HR) and blood oxygen saturation levels (SpO₂). Our designed sensor can remotely monitor BP, HR and SpO₂. Our device collects, evaluates, predicts and reads health data and then stores it on a remote platform named 'ThinkSpeak', which forms an Internet of Things (IoT) platform, with a 0.91 Organic Light-Emitting Diodes (OLED) screen display for viewing numerical health readings locally. We used a biomedical sensor device with an embedded signal condition unit, a single Photoplethysmography (PPG) signal was employed to derive and measure the PPG signal. A computer-based algorithm was generated which factored in selected beneficial parameters measured from a single bio-inspired PPG signal. The measured PPG signal was used to estimate the individual user's BP (both systolic and diastolic values), HR and SpO₂ respectively. An Automatic Multiscale-Based Peak (AMBP) detection algorithm was developed to obtain the maximum peak of the PPG signal. Furthermore, the developed sensor was benchmarked against two standard commercially available measurement

devices: a contec ambulatory BP sensor and a Braun pulse oximeter monitor. Our developed sensor is worn as a ring sensor and is interfaced with an Arduino 1010 WIFI MKR for remote health monitoring. Our estimated BP, HR and SpO₂ values were remotely monitored and a graphical representation was constructed.

INTRODUCTION

It has been estimated that there are 2.71 billion smartphone users worldwide in 2019 [1], with this number increasing yearly. The sensors integrated into smartphones, and their computational power enables wide usage in many areas of daily life, including health and activity monitoring. Parameters such as heart rate (HR) [[2], [3], [4], [5], [6],29,31,34,36,[38], [39], [40], [41]], blood oxygen saturation (SpO₂) [7,8,29,30], blood pressure (BP) [[9], [10], [11], [12], [13],37], number of walking steps [14], and type of activity [15] can be measured using a smartphone. Smartphone health monitoring does not replace certified medical devices, but it can be used as an approximate

alternative. Its advantages are multifunctionality, mobility, and non-invasiveness.

This study deals with the possibilities of HR, SpO₂, and BP monitoring using a smartphone. As conventional techniques and gold standards, ECG, gas chromatography (GC) [8], and mercury sphygmomanometry are used, respectively. These measurements are reliable, assuming the measurement is provided correctly by a trained physician. Moreover, for GC, invasive blood collection is necessary. For home monitoring, devices such as pulse oximeter (PO) or oscillometric sphygmomanometer, which are more user-friendly but usually less accurate, exist.

HR can be estimated using one of the following smartphone sensors: rear camera [[2], [3], [4], [5], [6],34,36], front camera [31,40], accelerometer [38,41], microphone [39], or sensors dedicated to HR and SpO₂ measurement [29]. The data from the rear camera are usually recorded from the finger, processed into the photoplethysmogram (PPG) waveform, and further analyzed to calculate HR [[2], [3], [4], [5], [6],34,36]. The front camera is used for the estimation of HR from the face. The data are processed similarly to the data from the rear camera, the PPG is computed, and further analysis is provided [31,40]. Using

the smartphone's built-in accelerometer, the mechanical activity of the heart can be measured (the seismocardiogram or ballistocardiogram) [38,41]. These signals are filtered, then the principal component analysis (PCA) [38] or linear power, quadratic spline decomposition and continuous wavelet transform [41] are performed, and finally, the peaks are searched. The microphone-based approach uses envelope calculation and peak detection [3]. Tayfur et al. [29] use sensors built-into the Samsung Galaxy S8 for HR and SpO₂ estimation along with the Samsung Health application for evaluation of the accuracy by comparisons with a vital signs monitor (VSM).

The SpO₂ level is a ratio between hemoglobin carrying oxygen and the total amount of hemoglobin in the blood [16]. Normal values of SpO₂ are 96–98% [16] or even up to 100%. It is usually measured by the PO. The measurement principle is similar to that with the smartphone. Both are based on photoplethysmography (PPG), which detects blood volume changes. The smartphone-based solution is simpler. Using the light-emitting diode (LED) light near to the camera is similar to the reflectance type measurement of the PO [17]. It approximates two light sources of different wavelengths by

the red and green RGB components of the recorded video [8]. The SpO₂ estimation using the smartphone is based on PPG features extraction and the use of mathematical equations [7,8]. Ding et al. [30] also calculate PPG and then use support vector machine (SVM)-based motion detection, feature extraction, and convolutional neural networks.

Arterial BP is usually measured in its two extremes – the highest (systolic) and the lowest (diastolic) [18]. Physiological values oscillate around 120/70 mmHg [18]. The most promising methods for BP estimation using the smartphone are based on the measurement of pulse (or vascular) transit time (PTT) [9,10]. PTT is defined as the time necessary for the pulse wave (blood) to travel from the heart to a periphery (fingertip). This feature is a function of the elasticity of the blood vessels and, thus, also with BP (lower elasticity means higher BP) [10]. PTT can be calculated from two signals measured by sensors placed on two different parts of the body (close to the heart and on the periphery). The combination of signals can be i) ECG and PPG [19,13,20] (mainstream method), ii) PPG and PPG [21], iii) skin strain (using a strain gauge) and PPG [22] in the case of conventional methods. Using the smartphone, the combination is a) two PPGs

from two opposite cameras (so-called photoplethysmographic imaging) [12], b) phonocardiogram (PCG) and PPG [9,10], and c) seismocardiogram and PPG [23]. BP is then calculated using equations [9]. Some methods need only one PPG for BP estimation [24,25,11,35,37,32]. These methods are based on feature extraction and the use of machine learning methods [24,25,35,37], cardiac output and total peripheral resistance estimation [11], and morphology and frequency analysis of PPG [32]. Dey [25] developed the Android application InstaBP for BP monitoring using a PPG sensor integrated into the flagship Samsung smartphone models. The limitation of the InstaBP application is that it does not work in all countries (e.g., the Czech Republic; tested on the Samsung Galaxy S7). The advantage of smartphone-based methods is the fact that they can evaluate BP from each beat, which is not possible in the case of cuff-based measurement [23]. Chandrasekhar et al. [26] recently introduced the innovative oscillometric finger pressing method. The authors utilized the iPhone X with a strain gauge array under the screen (3D Touch), which measures the pressure of fingertip placement. The second sensor used is a front camera, which measures blood volume oscillations in the finger. For the

recording, the authors developed an iOS application which leads the user while pressing the touch screen of the smartphone, because it is necessary to change the fingertip pressure during the measurement time. The BP estimation is similar to cuff-based oscillometric methods and is done offline. The technique of Luo et al. [31] records the video of the face, extracts 126 features and adds 29 meta-features, and uses the multilayer perceptron machine learning method. Peng et al. [33] use only the PCG recorded by the smartphone microphone to estimate BP. The principle is based on the extraction of heart-sounds features and the use of the SVM [33].

PROPOSED SYSTEM

Our method consists of two separate main stages: (1) self-supervised contrastive pre-training, and (2) supervised finetuning. First, we take a raw input video clip and detect regions of interest (RoI), namely the forehead and cheeks. This is done for two main reasons, first to enable more robust rPPG estimation, and second to allow for better user privacy protection. Next, subsequent to the detection of the RoI, we enter the first stage of our method where the RoI clip is processed by a data augmentation module to generate an augmented RoI clip. After this, the RoI and its augmented counterpart are passed

through an encoder and subsequently, the projection head to generate lower-level feature embeddings. This is done for all the input RoI clips. The contrastive loss is then used to learn strong representations by maximizing the similarity between embeddings belonging to the same RoI clip while minimizing the similarity between embeddings from separate RoI clips. Subsequently, in stage 2, we use the encoder from stage 1 and fine-tune it using the RoI clip as the input and the corresponding PPG signal as the output via smooth L1 loss. The architecture of our solution is illustrated in Figure 4. Through the following subsections, we describe each component of our solution mentioned above, in detail.

LITERATURE SURVEY

K. Shelley, S. Shelley, and C. Lake, "Pulse oximeter waveform: photoelectric plethysmography," Clinical Monitoring, vol. 2, 2001.

We investigate the hypothesis that the photoplethysmograph (PPG) waveform can be analyzed to infer regional venous oxygen saturation. **Methods.** Fundamental to the successful isolation of the venous saturation is the identification of PPG characteristics that are unique to the peripheral venous system. Two such characteristics have been identified. First, the peripheral venous waveform tends to reflect atrial contraction. Second, ventilation tends to move venous blood preferentially due to the low pressure and high compliance of the venous system.

Red (660 nm) and IR (940 nm) PPG waveforms were collected from 10 cardiac surgery patients using an esophageal PPG probe. These waveforms were analyzed using algorithms written in Mathematica. Four time-domain saturation algorithms (ArtSat, VenSat, ArtInstSat, VenInstSat) and four frequency-domain saturation algorithms (RespDC, RespAC, Cardiac, and Harmonic) were applied to the data set. Three of the algorithms for calculating venous saturation (VenSat, VenInstSat, and RespDC) demonstrate significant difference from ArtSat (the conventional time-domain algorithm for measuring arterial saturation) using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Bonferroni correction ($p < 0.0071$). **Conclusions.** This work introduces new algorithms for PPG analysis. Three algorithms (VenSat, VenInstSat, and RespDC) succeed in detecting lower saturation blood. The next step is to confirm the accuracy of the measurement by comparing them to a gold standard (i.e., venous blood gas).

A. R. Kavsaoglu, K. Polat, and M. Hariharan, “Non-invasive prediction of hemoglobin level using machine learning techniques with the ppg signal’s characteristics features,” Applied Soft Computing, vol. 37, pp. 983–991, 2015.

Hemoglobin can be measured normally after the analysis of the blood sample taken from the body and this measurement is named as invasive. Hemoglobin must continuously be measured to control the disease and its progression in people who go through hemodialysis and have diseases such as oligocythemia and anemia. This gives a perpetual feeling of pain to the people. This paper proposes a non-invasive method for the

prediction of the hemoglobin using the characteristic features of the PPG signals and different machine learning algorithms. In this work, PPG signals from 33 people were included in 10 periods and 40 characteristic features were extracted from them. In addition to these features, gender information (male or female), height (as cm), weight (as kg) and age of each subjects were also considered as the features. Blood count and hemoglobin level were measured simultaneously by using the “Hemocue Hb-201TM” device. Using the different machine learning regression techniques (classification and regression trees – CART, least squares regression – LSR, generalized linear regression – GLR, multivariate linear regression – MVLR, partial least squares regression – PLSR, generalized regression neural network – GRNN, MLP – multilayer perceptron, and support vector regression – SVR). RELIEFF feature selection (RFS) and correlation-based feature selection (CFS) were used to select the best features. Original features and selected features using RFS (10 features) and CFS (11 features) were used to predict the hemoglobin level using the different machine learning techniques. To evaluate the performance of the machine learning techniques, different performance measures such as mean absolute error – MAE, mean square error – MSE, R^2 (coefficient of determination), root mean square error – RMSE, Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and Index of Agreement – IA were used. The promising results were obtained (MSE-0.0027) using the selected features by RFS and SVR. Hence, the proposed method may clinically be used to predict the hemoglobin level of

human being clinically without taking and analyzing blood samples. Hemoglobin (Hb) is the basic component of the red blood cells. The Hb concentration in human blood is an important parameter both for each blood count and the evaluation of the physiologic state of an individual. Many invasive methods, (in which blood is taken from the patient physically and then analyzed) are used to measure the Hb concentration in today's technology. Besides the ailment experienced while taking the blood samples, the disadvantage of such invasive methods is the delay between the bloodletting and blood analysis [1].

P. Dehkordi, A. Garde, B. Molavi, J. M. Ansermino, and G. A. Dumont, “Extracting instantaneous respiratory rate from multiple photoplethysmogram respiratory-induced variations,” *Frontiers in Physiology*, vol. 9, p. 948, 2018.

In this study, we proposed a novel method for extracting the instantaneous respiratory rate (IRR) from the pulse oximeter photoplethysmogram (PPG). The method was performed in three main steps: (1) a time-frequency transform called synchrosqueezing transform (SST) was used to extract the respiratory-induced intensity, amplitude and frequency variation signals from PPG, (2) the second SST was applied to each extracted respiratory-induced variation signal to estimate the corresponding IRR, and (3) the proposed peak-conditioned fusion method then combined the IRR estimates to calculate the final IRR. We validated the implemented method with capnography and nasal/oral airflow as the reference RR using the limits of agreement (LOA) approach. Compared to simple fusion and single respiratory-induced

variation estimations, peak-conditioned fusion shows better performance. It provided a bias of 0.28 bpm with the 95% LOAs ranging from -3.62 to 4.17 , validated against capnography and a bias of 0.04 bpm with the 95% LOAs ranging from -5.74 to 5.82 , validated against nasal/oral airflow. This algorithm would expand the functionality of a conventional pulse oximetry beyond the measurement of heart rate and oxygen saturation to measure the respiratory rate continuously and instantly.

M. S. Lee, Y. K. Lee, D. S. Pae, M. T. Lim, D. W. Kim, and T. K. Kang, “Fast emotion recognition based on single pulse ppg signal with convolutional neural network,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 16, p. 3355, 2019.

Physiological signals contain considerable information regarding emotions. This paper investigated the ability of photoplethysmogram (PPG) signals to recognize emotion, adopting a two-dimensional emotion model based on valence and arousal to represent human feelings. The main purpose was to recognize short term emotion using a single PPG signal pulse. We used a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D CNN) to extract PPG signal features to classify the valence and arousal. We split the PPG signal into a single 1.1 s pulse and normalized it for input to the neural network based on the personal maximum and minimum values. We chose the dataset for emotion analysis using physiological (DEAP) signals for the experiment and tested the 1D CNN as a binary classification (high or low valence and arousal), achieving the short-term emotion recognition of 1.1 s with 75.3% and 76.2% valence and arousal accuracies, respectively, on the DEAP data.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

ARUDINO:

The Arduino is a family of microcontroller boards to simplify electronic design, prototyping and experimenting for artists, hackers, hobbyists, but also many professionals. People use it as brains for their robots, to build new digital music instruments, or to build a system that lets your house plants tweet you when they're dry. Arduinos (we use the standard Arduino Uno) are built around an ATmega microcontroller — essentially a complete computer with CPU, RAM, Flash memory, and input/output pins, all on a single chip. Unlike, say, a Raspberry Pi, it's designed to attach all kinds of sensors, LEDs, small motors and speakers, servos, etc. directly to these pins, which can read in or output digital or analog voltages between 0 and 5 volts. The Arduino connects to your computer via USB, where you program it in a simple language

(C/C++, similar to Java) from inside the free Arduino IDE by uploading your compiled code to the board. Once programmed, the Arduino can run with the USB link back to your computer, or stand-alone without it — no keyboard or screen needed, just power.

DHT TEMPERATURE & HUMIDITY SENSORS.

These sensors are very basic and slow, but are great for hobbyists who want to do some basic data logging. The DHT sensors are made of two parts, a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor. There is also a very basic chip inside that does some analog to digital conversion and spits out a digital signal with the temperature and humidity. The digital signal is fairly easy to read using any microcontroller. Humidity is the measure of water vapour present in the air. The level of humidity in air affects various physical, chemical and biological processes. In industrial applications, humidity can affect the business cost of the products, health and safety of the employees. So, in semiconductor industries and control system industries measurement of humidity is very important. Humidity measurement determines the amount of moisture present in the gas that can be a mixture of water vapour, nitrogen, argon or pure gas etc... Humidity sensors are of two types based

on their measurement units. They are a relative humidity sensor and Absolute humidity sensor. DHT11 is a digital temperature and humidity sensor.

BUZZERS

In common parlance a Buzzer is a signaling device that is not a loudspeaker. It can be mechanical, electromechanical, or electronic (a piezo transducer). BeStar produces Buzzers in every available configuration for a wide variety of applications. A Piezo transducer can produce the sound for panel mount buzzers, household goods, medical devices and even very loud sirens. When a lower frequency is required an electromagnetic buzzer can fill the need. These are very common in automotive chimes and higher end clinical diagnostic devices. The BeStar buzzer range includes self drive units with their own drive circuitry (indicators), or external drive units, which allow the designer the flexibility to create their own sound patterns.

MEMS:

Microelectromechanical systems (MEMS), also written as micro-electro-mechanical systems (or microelectronic and microelectromechanical systems) and the related micro mechatronics and

microsystems constitute the technology of microscopic devices, particularly those with moving parts. They merge at the nanoscale into nanoelectromechanical systems (NEMS) and nanotechnology. MEMS are also referred to as micromachines in Japan and microsystem technology (MST) in Europe. MEMS are made up of components between 1 and 100 micrometers in size (i.e., 0.001 to 0.1 mm), and MEMS devices generally range in size from 20 micro metres to a millimetre (i.e., 0.02 to 1.0 mm), although components arranged in arrays (e.g., digital micromirror devices) can be more than 1000 μm^2 . [1] They usually consist of a central unit that processes data (an integrated circuit chip such as microprocessor) and several components that interact with the surroundings (such as microsensors). [2] Because of the large surface area to volume ratio of MEMS, forces produced by ambient electromagnetism (e.g., electrostatic charges and magnetic moments), and fluid dynamics (e.g., surface tension and viscosity) are more important design considerations than with larger scale mechanical devices. MEMS technology is distinguished from molecular nanotechnology or molecular electronics in that the latter must also consider surface chemistry. The potential of very small machines was appreciated before the

technology existed that could make them (see, for example, Richard Feynman's famous 1959 lecture *There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom*). MEMS became practical once they could be fabricated using modified semiconductor device fabrication technologies, normally used to make electronics.[3] These include molding and plating, wet etching (KOH, TMAH) and dry etching (RIE and DRIE), electrical discharge machining (EDM), and other technologies capable of manufacturing small devices.

CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed a two-stage method based on the use of self-supervised contrastive pre-training and fine-tuning for remote PPG estimation and HR prediction from facial videos. We showcased that introducing contrastive learning as a pre-training measure helps in more robust learning of the network for the downstream task of rPPG estimation. Subsequently, we performed thorough experiments to validate the different design choices of the method such as the video representation learning technique, the pairing strategy, the augmentations used in the self-supervised pre-training, and the different facial regions to be used as inputs for the entire method. Our comprehensive experiments showed that our self-supervised approach

outperforms many fully supervised techniques to approach the state-of-the-art, while also being less reliant on output labels during the training stage.

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